

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SELF-GOVERNANCE IN ATHLETES

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Annotation. Athletes' self-management characteristics have a significant impact on their performance in sports. There is a great need for programs to restore the optimal psychological and physiological state after the race, as well as the rapid recovery of self-management functions in the short period between races. This article analyzes the psychological characteristics of the athlete and identifies disorders in self-management.

Keywords: self-management, self-control, mental stability, temperament, motivation.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ САМОУПРАВЛЕНИЯ
У СПОРТСМЕНОВ

Аннотация. Особенности самоуправления у спортсменов оказывают значительное влияние на их результаты в спорте. Существует большая потребность в программах восстановления оптимального психологического и физиологического состояния после состязания, а также быстрого восстановления функций самоуправления в короткий период между состязаниями. В данной статье анализируются психологические особенности спортсмена и определяются нарушения в самоконтроле.

Ключевые слова: самоуправление, самоконтроль, психическая устойчивость, темперамент, мотивация.

СПОРТЧИЛАРДА ЎЗ-ЎЗИНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ ПСИХОЛОГИК
ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

Аннотация. Спортчиларда ўз-ўзини бошқаришнинг хусусиятлари уларнинг спортдаги натижаларига сезиларли даражада таъсир кўрсатади. Мусобақадан сўнг оптимал психологик ва физиологик ҳолатни тиклаш, шунингдек, беллашувлар оралигидаги қисқа муддатда ўзини-ўзи бошқариш функцияларини тезкор тиклаш бўйича дастурларга эҳтиёж катта. Ушбу мақолада спортчининг психологик хусусиятлари таҳлил қилинади ва ўзини-ўзи бошқаришдаги бузилишлар аниқланади.

Калит сўзлар: ўз-ўзини бошқариш, ўз-ўзини назорат қилиш, руҳий барқарорлик, темперамент, мотивация.

INTRODUCTION

It is important for boxers to develop self-control. Because boxers are fast and fierce. It is also very emotional. In post-race cases, it is difficult to re-establish an optimal psychological sports condition when winning and losing. A complex self-program is needed, especially to bring athletes who have lost consciousness in a competition back into the ring.

Self-management involves controlling one's actions, emotions, and thoughts toward long-term goals. More specifically, emotional self-management refers to the ability to control destructive emotions and impulses [3]. Things such as emotions, values, and priorities affect how we achieve our goals and how we strive for them. If athletes are psychologically prepared for negative thinking, emotional instability, and stress-related problems during training, the athlete will take control of the outcome, regardless of the outcome, and move on to the next goal. in

essence, maturity reflects the ability to patiently and thoughtfully respond to emotional, social, and cognitive threats in the environment. If this definition reminds you of consciousness, it is no coincidence - consciousness is really related to the ability to self-regulate [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In developing the presentation of the self-management system, I propose four levels, a self-regulatory model and a four-level model of the professional activity-related skills model [5]. According to the current comparison, there are some changes in the content of levels in the model:

1. Psychophysiological degree - the ability to emotional and self-manage psychophysiological conditions.
2. Socio-psychological level - the ability to interact with oneself in a social process.
3. Psychological level:
 - a) ability to regulate activities;
 - b) the ability to self-manage and self-improve;
 - c) the ability to show willpower, mobilize energy.
4. The spiritual level is the highest ability of self-government to direct the individual to the higher values and meanings of being.

Self-management is the ability to regulate an individual's professional self-awareness.

Psychophysiological level - the ability to self-regulate emotional and psychophysiological conditions: from simple self-regulatory skills (individual methods of recovery psycho-emotional balance and improved physical condition) -complex (achieved by using special methods of self-regulation. Use of special methods of self-regulation (metadology), the peculiarities of the profession in the difficult and extreme conditions of the corresponding professional activity. to the extent that the individual carries out self-regulation without social interaction, without being.

Socio-psychological level - the process of self-regulation ability is an interaction that is directly related to social professional activity, as well as an interaction that indirectly affects the success of any social professional activity impact (e.g., family relationships, relationships with friends, etc.). It includes the previous Level 1 in the social context (as well as self-regulation of emotional and psychophysiological states using social strategies) .In this case, self-regulation is in many ways social -related to normative rules and life experience.

Psychological level: a) the ability to regulate activities: goal setting, planning, necessary design, conditions for professional activity and ways to improve it and its effectiveness; ability to monitor the success of its implementation and self-control (level of awareness at all stages of higher professional activity: motive - goal - necessary conditions - direction of action - evaluation of the result - necessary correction - new result); with intellectual reflection related;

b) the ability to self-manage and self-improve (self-improvement) .Awareness to achieve the inner harmony necessary for success, self-o to know what kind of professional activity to carry out). Personal thinking plays a crucial role in the development of professional activities in the areas of personality, motivation and need, in accordance with the requirements of understanding the possible and powerful character traits and regulating personal characteristics; related to personal reflection;

c) the ability to show willpower, to mobilize energy for self-regulation; activity goal and efforts to achieve the goal of self-improvement. Developed form depends on personal self-management ability High self-management skills category , because it creates the conditions for spirituality in any activity that affects the development and self-awareness of the individual, including professional activity.

The spiritual level is the highest ability of self-government (self-regulation at all levels related to the whole is conditioned by the highest values and meanings of being; it belongs to the highest moral principles). It focuses on the evolution of the level of professional activity (the transition from a selfish "I" to a spiritual "I"). A person does not carry out his / her professional activity without financial incentives, but it is important to improve the activity itself and thus self-motivation in self-management factor.

G.Yu. Eysenck test, This method is based on a set of tests to determine the individual-typological characteristics of G. Eysenck, in which the individual is studied using indicators on the scales of "extroversion", "introversion", "neuroticism". This allows you to study the characteristics of athletes. I.P. Summarizing the views of Pavlov and K. Yung, G. Eisenk studied the individuality in the two-parameter line as "extroversion" (external), "introversion" (internal), "neuroticism" (emotional instability and stability) - a product of emotional balance. and place the information obtained in a diagram of temperament types named by Hippocrates as a special key. This means that the "unique" feature of "extroversion" is its "excitability" and "mobility", while the "introvert" is a bit "slow". "Instability" is the result of an imbalance in the process of starting and braking.

Figure 1.

RESULTS

The technique was performed on 18 boxers from the national team who came for in-depth psychological diagnosis. Their average age Average age = 19.3

E age difference <5

Then out of 18 boxers

Sanguine -10 people 55.5%, choleric-6 people 33.3%, phlegmatic-0, melancholic-1 person 5.5%. (Figure 1).

Extraversion was 100% and introversion was 0%. At the same time, in almost all boxers, extraversion resulted in Mexroversion > 8.

On the neuroticism scale, 6 boxers have low, 8 have average, and 2 have more than 14 (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

DISCUSSION

The ability to fight is closely related to a boxer's mental state and ability to behave. Fear, cowardice, anxiety, depression, confusion can prevent an athlete from practicing combat technical skills; his understanding of his technical and physical fitness, his experience has a positive effect on the boxer's mental state [4].

CONCLUSIONS

The fact that boxers have a mostly choleric or sanguine temperament makes them more likely to box. It is also a factor in the sport to be fast, aggressive, intense, technically and tactically superior to the opponent. But outside of sports, these traits are much more dangerous socially and behaviorally. Boxers' reactions to stressful situations can be very dangerous for themselves and others. And this will negatively affect the results of the competition.

For this reason, it is important for boxers to develop self-management skills in stressful situations.

References

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